

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08th October 2022

Accepted: 18th October 2022

Online: 28th October 2022

KEY WORDS

From the first days of independence, the organization of the national economy in accordance with the geographical location and mentality of our country and developing it on the basis of the demand of the time has been determined. It was very difficult to organize and implement socio-economic reforms in the early days. Because the scope of factors negatively affecting the process of reforms in these periods was large, the main ones were as follows:

- slowness in abandoning the planned economy and administrative management, as well as inexperience in introducing the laws and principles of the market economy;
- the priority, or rather hegemony, of the share of the agricultural sector in the structure of GDP created in the country;
- both physical and spiritual obsolescence of the main means of production used in practice;

THE ROLE OF INDUSTRY REGULATIONS IN THE CONSISTENT DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

Murodova N.O.

QarMI Department of Business and
Innovation Management
senior teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7261510>

ABSTRACT

In this article the comparative analysis of development of the tourist sphere is studied. It is proved that the initial periods of independence of the country's leaders and economists did not pay attention to the tourism sector. It is proved that the tourism industry it require little cost, but get a lot of economic and social effects. In recent years, special attention is paid to the tourism industry, timely and periodic regulatory acts. As a result, new jobs are being created and the economic and social spheres of the Republic are developing rapidly.

- for a short period of time, 16-8% of the State budget will be equivalent to income in the form of grants and subsidies, as well as foreign political expenses, which did not exist before, suddenly appear in the budget expenses;

- and finally, the instability of interstate economic, financial and economic relations between the republics of the Union, etc.

Therefore, if the above negative indicators are left as they are, our national economy would not develop, but stagnate or decline.

Therefore, the existing situation began to demand the acceleration of reforms.

It is worth noting that after we started independently implementing the new economic policy, reforms were introduced first in the production and then in the service sector. As an example, it can be said that this process has been accelerated in the banking, insurance, trade and marketing spheres of service provision, as well as in a certain sense in the sphere of

education. A number of benefits were granted to commercial banks. They have been exempted from basic taxes for several years and have been given an opportunity to update their material and technical base. A similar situation could be observed in insurance entities. Since 2005, attention to academic lyceums and vocational colleges has been sharply increased, and a large part of the national income has been directed to the construction of new buildings and facilities for them in a short period of time. As a result, thousands of new college and lyceum buildings and additional facilities serving them were built. In order to develop school education, a program covering the years 2004-2009 was created. In order to timely and fully finance the measures provided for in the program, a special fund for the development of school education was established. However, there is a service sector in the national economy where you can earn a high profit at low cost. The name of this industry, which exists only in some countries, is tourism.

I can say with satisfaction that our republic has the right to take the lead among the Central Asian countries in the organization and development of local, regional and even international tourism. The buildings, constructions and historical monuments left by our ancestors in our country are colorful and diverse. In fact, "Uzbekistan has a huge potential for tourism and recreation, it has a total of 7,400 cultural heritage objects, 209 of which are four museum cities - "Ichan Castle in Khiva", "Historical Center of Bukhara", "Historical center of Shahrisabz city", is located in the territory of "Samarkand city" and is included in the UNESCO world heritage list.

All of them are one of the sources that directly serve the development of tourism and increase the flow of tourists, in a word, they provide the opportunity to obtain high socio-economic results at low cost. However, in our country, since the early days of independence, insufficient attention was paid to the development of tourism in accordance with the needs of the times.

It is worth mentioning here that there are leaders in this field among the CIS countries. They are among the top 10 countries in the world according to some indicators in the field of tourism. One of them is Georgia: "According to the National Tourism Administration of the country, in 2018, Georgia's income from tourism was 3.0 billion. exceeded the US dollar. In 2018, the number of tourists who came to Georgia increased by 14.9% compared to 2017 and reached 8.7 million people.

The positive performance of Georgia, which left the former union at the same time as us, in the field of tourism shows! However, its territory is smaller than the territory of our only Navoi region. 65-70% of the land area of this region consists of mountains. The population of Fergana region is only slightly more. I am sure that the historical buildings and monuments are few times less than ours, but not much. Let's focus on one more indicator:

There are 2.35 tourists for every Georgian living in Georgia (Georgia's population is 3.7 million people). With this indicator, it would not be wrong to say that Georgia is among the top 10 countries in the world in terms of tourism services. This is the result of the Georgian government and economists paying serious attention to the organization and development of tourism in the country at the right time, that is,

from the first day of independence. That is why Georgians are making unprecedented progress in the field of tourism among the CIS countries.

Taking into account the priority role of the tourism sector in the national economy and the possibility of the socio-economic development of the country, during the next two years serious and significant attention was paid to the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, like all branches and sectors. Along with changes and additions to the existing regulatory documents aimed at the development of tourism, based on the needs of the time, new ones are also adopted and introduced into the field with consistent speed.

Effective organization, implementation and coordination of tourism services in the Republic is carried out on the basis of the Law "On Tourism" developed and put into practice on the basis of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On the basis of this law adopted on August 20, 1999, the decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the decisions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers, and the guidelines of the State Committee for Tourism Development are being coordinated.

The Law "On Tourism" consists of 22 articles and is filled with indicators that directly serve the organization and development of tourism. In the law, the rights and obligations of the entities directly and indirectly related to tourism are also specified in the event of insurance and force majeure.

Also, on the basis of the decision No. 53 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 10, 2015 "On some aspects of tourism development in

the Republic of Uzbekistan", a special Regulation was developed.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the tourism sector was recognized for the first time as a strategic branch of the economy. The concept of measures for the development of the medium-term tourism sector, which covers the years 2017-2021, developed in order to create a positive image of Uzbekistan in the field, is being consistently implemented.

According to the decree, the issues of mandatory certification of which business entities are engaged in tourism activities and which services they can provide have been clearly defined. In order to facilitate the arrival and departure of foreign citizens to Uzbekistan, issues of liberalization and simplification of visa procedures for citizens of a number of countries, if they come to our country in less than 30 days, were also mentioned. In order to create convenience for residents and non-residents entering our country at the international airport and railway stations, a positive solution to the issue of organizing separate passageways, as in developed countries, was also discussed. The Central Bank and the commercial banks under its jurisdiction were assigned the task of organizing currency exchange offices for foreign and local tourists in accordance with the current requirements. In short, the main purpose of the Decree is to increase the share of income from tourism in the country's GDP, to improve people's living standards by eliminating social problems in the country by creating new jobs, to increase income to the local

and republican budgets, and finally, the available opportunities and showing the potential to the whole world and achieving high socio-economic development on the scale of the Central Asian region.

In this regard, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 2, 2016 "On the organization of the activities of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PQ-2666 is also important. In accordance with this decision, the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be considered the legal successor of the National Company "Uzbekturizm" in terms of all obligations and contracts, including international obligations and agreements, and all unitary enterprises under the company's control shall be subject to current requirements. It was also determined that it will be renamed accordingly and transferred to the committee. Resolution No. 137 of the Cabinet of Ministers of March 15, 2017 "On measures to further support and develop the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan" under the State Committee for Tourism Development, the non-budget tourism sector committee was the basis for the establishment of the support fund. In turn, the Regulation on the formation of fund funds and the procedure for their effective use was also approved. In the regulation, the sources of formation of extra-budgetary fund funds and directions of spending were indicated. In addition, responsible persons were also noted in cases of purposeless and unreasonable use of these funds. The establishment of the fund will undoubtedly help to expand the possibilities of timely and complete

financing of the measures implemented in the field of tourism.

Decision No. 355 of the Cabinet of Ministers dated June 5, 2017 "On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for certification of tour operators and hotel services" also has a special place in the activity of the sector. The regulation stipulates mandatory certification of tour operators and hotels serving tourists. The main goal of mandatory certification is to guarantee quality and safe service to foreign and domestic tourists. Another effective task is to awaken the desire to visit our country again with friends and relatives in the future.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2018 "On additional measures to create favorable conditions for the development of the tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-5326 marked a unique stage in the development of the sector was the basis for the beginning. As stipulated in the decree, starting from the second decade of February 2018, the procedure of free arrival and departure without a visa was introduced for the citizens of Israel, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, Singapore, the Republic of Turkey and Japan for a period of 30 days from the day of entering the territory of the country.

Also, the State Committee for the Development of Tourism, the Ministry of Public Education, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, the Council of the Federation of Trade Unions, the Committee of Women and Girls, the Charitable Community Fund "Mahalla" and Nurani Foundation's "Travel around Uzbekistan!", which provides for the organization of tourism-excursions in the

regions of the republic for various segments of the population. the domestic tourism development program was approved. According to the program:

- for students of educational institutions - during vacations and weekends;
- for employees of organizations - on weekends, national holidays and holidays, especially during the low tourism season;
- for socially vulnerable sections of the population, pensioners, war and labor veterans - during the year, actively using recreation in sanatoriums and spas;
- for the elderly, young families, activists of citizens' assemblies, women and representatives of other public associations
- the organization of domestic tourism during the low season of tourism was specially shown.

Another distinctive feature of this decree is that, starting from February 10, 2018, a list of 39 countries was announced, which introduced a simplified procedure for issuing visas for citizens. A number of financial incentives were also provided to newly established tour operators and investors who built new hotels. This, in turn, creates an opportunity to create favorable conditions for accelerating the development of foreign tourism along with domestic tourism in the country.

Implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5326 dated February 3, 2018 "On additional organizational measures to create favorable conditions for the development of the tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan", as well as Tourism It was focused on increasing the efficiency of the State Development Committee, its position in attracting foreign investments in the tourism sector, the entry of foreign

tourists to the country and the development of domestic tourism.

Decision PQ-3510 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 6, 2018 "On measures to further improve the activities of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. According to it, the organizational structure of the State Committee for Tourism Development, the structure of the central apparatus, regional administrations and the model structure of the Department of Tourism Development were approved. It is planned to gradually increase the number of employees working in the central office to 107 by January 1, 2019. At the same time, changes and additions were made to the regulatory documents adopted for the development of early tourism based on the needs of the time.

The next decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2018 "On measures to ensure the rapid development of domestic tourism" provides further support for the above-mentioned normative documents. The peculiarity of this decision is that now, based on the aforementioned decision, every business entity has the opportunity to take its employees on tourist trips without difficulty, that is, cultural and educational recreation of its workers and employees at the expense of excess financial resources at their disposal. 'providing, and ultimately, he had a favorable opportunity to increase labor productivity. The decision did not leave a reason for unnecessary harassment of the company's management by state inspection bodies in the future. In a word, it was possible to get rid of corruption due to the legal solution of the social problem.

Generally, advertising is considered as the engine of commercial and economic activity. Actually it is. Therefore, the role of advertising in the development of tourism is incomparable. But advertising is given and displayed at the expense of a certain financial amount. With this decision, tourism-related outdoor advertising placed by the State Committee for Tourism Development and local executive authorities was equated to social advertising. In agreement with the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, governorates of the regions and Tashkent city, in 2018-2020, at least 100 places in each region of the republic will be taken into account. It was determined that external advertising related to domestic tourism should be installed impartially.

This, in turn, multiplies the possibility of serving as a basis for the rapid development of tourism. Also, in order to expand the opportunity for the citizens of the country to spend tourism-related expenses in a timely manner, to organize rest at the right time, commercial banks operating in the economy have a license to operate in the field of citizen tourism. 10 miles for purchasing tourist tours across the Republic of Uzbekistan from subjects. It was recommended to allocate consumer loans up to soums and create a possibility to cover the loan from wages. On January 5, 2019, our President signed another normative document that creates a favorable opportunity for the rapid development of tourism. Decree "On additional measures for rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan". The main focus of the decree is to create a number of favorable opportunities for foreign and domestic tourists and business

entities directly and indirectly related to the tourism sector.

One of the main steps in this regard is the approval of the Tourism Development Concept for 2019-2025. As stipulated in the decree, attention is paid to the organization of the transport logistics service for tourists in accordance with the requirements of the time and to the consistent improvement of its quality.

A factor that directly affects the attraction of tourists is the provision of qualified personnel in the field. Therefore, the decree focuses on this direction and the need to improve the system of training, retraining and professional development of personnel for the tourism sector is emphasized. Also, the issue of speeding up the internal and external airport service is included in the central links of the decree. In this, the task of increasing the flow of tourists through the direction of "pilgrimage" tourism, including the issue of attracting airlines to open regular flights from Indonesia, has been set aside.

Based on this regulatory document, citizens of 109 countries on the globe will be given the right to obtain a residence permit in the republic if they fulfill the following requirements:

- in the Tashkent region and the city of Tashkent - in an amount not less than the equivalent of 400,000 US dollars;
- in Samarkand, Bukhara, Namangan, Andijan, Fergana and Khorezm regions - in an amount not less than the equivalent of 200,000 US dollars;
- in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and other regions of the republic - in the case of purchasing real estate in an amount not less than the equivalent of 100,000 US dollars.

The 7-year target indicators of the implementation of the Tourism Sector Development Concept have been approved. It shows how many hotels will be opened during this period, how much the number of foreign and domestic tourists will increase, and how much and how many percent the income from tourism and its share in GDP will increase, respectively.

From February 1, 2019, the number of countries whose citizens will be subject to a visa-free regime for a period of 30 days has reached 76;

It was also decided to introduce additional (non-electronic) entry visa categories for certain groups of foreign citizens visiting the Republic of Uzbekistan. Including:

1. "Citizen" - a 2-year visa issued to persons born in the Republic of Uzbekistan and their family members based on the invitation letter of relatives who are citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and permanently reside in its territory;
2. "Student visa" - a one-year visa issued to foreign students admitted to educational institutions located in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the request of educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ministries, agencies and organizations under the jurisdiction of educational institutions. visa;
3. "Academic visa" - a foreigner who wants to carry out scientific research and pedagogical activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan at the request of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, scientific research organizations, higher education institutions, ministries or agencies in the Republic of Uzbekistan visa for individuals for a period of 3 months to 2 years;
4. "Medical visa" - a visa issued for a period of up to 3 months for foreign citizens

entering the Republic of Uzbekistan for treatment at the suggestion of a medical institution;

5. "Pilgrim visa" - foreign citizens entering to study the cultural-historical and religious heritage and traditions of Uzbekistan according to the application of the Committee on Religious Affairs under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and subjects of tourist activity A visit visa for up to 2 months has been introduced.

On the basis of timely adopted and implemented regulatory documents, an open door policy is being pursued with the neighboring republics, whose majority share the same religion and language. Also, serious socio-economic achievements are being made due to the fact that tourists from dozens of distant foreign countries are given the convenience and freedom to come and go to the country without issuing a visa within a month. For example, "in January-September 2018, more than one million people from neighboring Tajikistan came to Uzbekistan, correspondingly the same number of citizens came from Uzbekistan to Tajikistan"³. See, due to the conditions created, the flow of tourists from one neighboring country has increased dramatically over the past nine months. Calculate how much money is circulating through our trade and commercial banks even if each of them spends 100 US dollars on average.

Also, we would not be wrong to say that the following statistics are the result of serious attention to this field: "During the years 2010-2017, the volume of export of tourism services doubled and reached 546.9 million US dollars in 2017, and -1 in 2018. 041 million US dollars. Until 2016, the growth rate of the number of foreign

visitors was 8 percent on average, and in 2017 - 7 percent, exceeding 2.69 million people. At the end of 2018, 5.3 million foreign tourists visited the republic. As a result of taking measures aimed at supporting and protecting the private sector, the number of tourism organizations, which was 398 in 2015, reached 950 by the end of 2018, and the number of hotel establishments - from 661 to 900.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the next 2 years, more than 10 normative documents aimed at the convenient organization, coordination and development of tourism were adopted. All these documents require each other and

are being accepted in full compliance with the rules of logic. Based on the demand of the period, this process continues consistently. The main reason for saying this is that, although we have an objective need to develop tourism, this area has been left to its own devices over the years. In a word, it developed according to its own flow. Therefore, the tiny mountainous country of the former union is a few steps ahead of us in the field of tourism today. This should be a lesson for us, and besides, we should take an example from it, use all the possibilities in the field of tourism, and continue to strengthen our efforts in this field.

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism". August 20, 1999.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Strategy of actions on five priority areas of development of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" of February 7, 2017.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. 4861. December 2, 2016.
4. Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the regulation on the procedure for certification of tour operator and hotel services". 05 June 2017.
5. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the "Primary program of measures for the development of tourism in 2018-2019". August 16, 2017.
6. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the activities of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" of February 6, 2018.
7. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures for the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan", January 5, 2019.
8. CONCEPT "Development of the tourism industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025". Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2019 No. PF-5611. Appendix 1.
9. <https://news.mail.ru> 10. <https://www.kavkaz-uzel.eu>